

A Field-Based Study on Self-Help Groups in Tanuku Mandal of West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract:

Based on a field visit, this study reveals that if rural women under the umbrella of Self-help Groups (SHGs henceforth SHG will be used) are appropriately guided and supported with backward and forward linkages, they will earn income, whatever their qualification. The study was conducted at Velpur village Panchayat, Tanuku Mandal of West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh on March 23, 2025. The study was conducted among five women of different Self Help Groups (SHGs). The primary methodology of the survey was PRA, which earlier was known as Participatory Rural Appraisal, now popularly known as PRA. Both Group Discussion and Focus Group Discussion were conducted as part of PRA. For the Focus Group Discussion, the interview method was used. Five members of four different SHGs were interviewed to understand income generation activities. Since the interview was conducted in the presence of other members of SHGs and government officials, it can be assumed that the information they provided was authentic.

Keywords: Andhra Pradesh/Velpur village, Income, PRA, SHG, and Women members

Introduction

After the successful experiment of Self-help groups (SHGs) by Professor Muhammad Yunus in Bangladesh under the umbrella of Grameen Bank, the concept of Self-help groups (SHG) has become popular in the world for the empowerment of women through income generation activities. Prof Yunus, in his book *Banker to the Poor*, has highlighted some advantages of self-employment over wage employment. Some of the important points are presented below:

1. The hours are flexible and can adapt to fit any family situation. It allows people to choose between running a business full-time or part-time when they need to meet crises or put their business on hold and work full-time for a salary.
2. Self-employment is tailor-made for anyone who is street-smart and has many acquired from books and technical schools. This means the illiterate and the poor can exploit their strengths, rather than be held back by their weaknesses
3. It allows a person to turn hobbies they enjoy into gainful employment.
4. It offers a way out of welfare dependency, not just to become wage slaves, but to open a store or start a manufacturing business.
5. It gives those who have just been fired from a job moral support to start a business before they become depressed and isolated.
6. It gives the victims of prejudice who would not be hired because of their colour or national origin a chance to earn a living.
7. The average cost of creating a self-employment job is ten, twenty, or a hundred times cheaper than creating an employment job.
8. It helps isolated poor person gain self-confidence, step by step.

The author studied across the country many SHGs formed by rural women members and documented in books and research articles for the benefit of readers and researchers. The studies were carried out in different states of India from time to time viz., Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarhh, Gujarat, Jammu and Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, etc., and observed that after forming self-help groups women felt empowered. Because of the earnings of the women members, the standard of living of the family also went up. The author observed that by

investing comparatively less capital, one can earn substantial income for a below-poverty family, which can help cross the poverty line (Chatterjee, 2017, 2018, and 2019).

It is pertinent to mention that SHGs are informal groups of people who come together to address their common problems. A critical feature of a self-help group is mutual support – people helping each other. In the case of rural SHG, essential features are monthly/weekly savings and rotating the money among the members with a low interest rate (FAO, 1992). When the discussion of SHG crops up, the Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India's National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), which by restructuring Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) was implemented, is highlighted. NRLM has been renamed DAY-NRLM (Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission) since March 29, 2016. A few lines about DAY-NRLM from the website rbi.org.in are highlighted here.

Women SHGs and their Federations

- a) DAY-NRLM promotes affinity-based women Self Help Groups (SHGs). However, only in case of groups to be formed with persons with disabilities and other special categories like elders and transgenders, DAY-NRLM may have both men and women in the Self-Help Groups.
- b) Women SHGs under DAY-NRLM consist of 10-20 members. In the case of special SHGs, i.e., groups in difficult areas, groups with disabled persons, and groups formed in remote tribal areas, this number may be a minimum of 5 members.
- c) Federations of Self-Help Groups formed at village, gram panchayat, cluster, or higher level may be registered under appropriate Acts prevailing in their respective states.
- d) SHGs should be practicing 'Panchasutras,' i.e., regular meetings, regular savings, regular inter-lending, timely repayment, and up-to-date books of accounts.

Financial Assistance to the SHGs

- a) **Revolving Fund:** The Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD) will support Revolving Fund (RF) as a corpus ranging between Rs. 10,000 and Rs.15,000 per SHG to strengthen their institutional and financial management capacity and build a good credit history within the group. SHGs in existence for a minimum period of 3/6 months and follow the norms of good SHGs known as 'Panchasutras,' viz., regular meetings,

regular savings, regular internal lending, regular recoveries, and maintenance of proper books of accounts, and which have not received any RF earlier will be eligible for such support.

b) Capital Subsidy: No capital subsidy would be sanctioned to any SHG under DAY-NRLM.

c) Community Investment Support Fund (CIF): MoRD will provide CIF to the SHGs promoted under DAY-NRLM in all blocks. The funds will be routed through the village/cluster level federations and maintained in perpetuity by the federations. The federations may use the CIF to advance loans to the SHGs and/or undertake common/collective socio-economic activities.

d) Interest Subvention: DAY-NRLM has a provision for interest subvention for women SHGs.

e) Role of banks: Opening of Savings/Current Accounts: The role of banks would commence with the opening of accounts for all the SHGs including those having members with disability and for the federations of SHGs. The SHGs promoting savings habits among their members would be eligible to open savings bank accounts. Banks are advised to maintain separate savings and loan accounts for SHGs. Banks are advised to open savings accounts of federations of SHGs at the village, gram panchayat, cluster, or higher level. These accounts may be categorized as savings accounts for the 'Association of Persons'. The 'Know Your Customer' (KYC) norms for the signatories of such accounts, as specified from time to time by the Reserve Bank of India, would be applicable. SHGs and their federations may be encouraged to transact through their respective savings/cash credit accounts.

About the Study and Methodology:

The study was conducted on March 23, 2025, at Velpur village Panchayat, Tanuku Mandal of West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh. It was conducted among five women from different Self-Help Groups (SHGs). The primary methodology of the survey was PRA, which earlier was known as Participatory Rural Appraisal, now popularly known as PRA. As part of PRA, both Group Discussion and Focus Group Discussion were conducted based on the interview method.

Photo: Self Help Group Meeting at Velpur village Panchayat, Tanuku Mandal of West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh.

About Velpur (source: onefivenine.com/india/villages)

Velpur is a Village in Tanuku Mandal in the West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh.

Velpur 2011 Census: The total population of the village was 22768, and the number of houses was 6781. The female population was 51 percent. The overall literacy rate was 72 percent, but the female literacy rate was 35.7 percent. At glance overall situation of Velpur village can be seen from the following table.

Table: 1 Population and Literacy rate of the village

Census Parameter	Census Data
Total Population	22768
Total No of Houses	6781
Female Population %	51.2 %
Total Literacy rate %	71.8 %
Female Literacy rate	35.7 %
Scheduled Tribes Population %	0.5 %
Scheduled Caste Population %	12.8 %
Working Population %	42.1 %
Child(0 -6) Population by 2011	1881
Girl Child(0 -6) Population % by 2011	51.4 %

Source: www.onefivenine.com/india/villages

Field Situation:

During the study, it was reported that there were 389 SHGs with 3881 members in the village of Velpur. There were nine Village Organizations (VOs). On an average, 44 SHGs were under the umbrella of one VO. Five members of four different SHGs were interviewed to understand income generation activities. Since the interview was conducted in the presence of other members of SHGs and government officials, it can be assumed that the information they provided was authentic.

Case 1: Durga Mahalakshmi Group

The SHG was set up on May 5, 2005, with 10 members belonging to Other Caste (OC). The initial monthly saving for each member was Rs. 100, which was enhanced to Rs. 200. The SHG's Corpus Fund was Rs. 3.25 lakh, and the SHG was provided a bank loan amounting to Rs. 20 lakh. Two cases from this SHG are presented here.

i) Sunkara Lakshmi (46 years/5th pass) borrowed eight times; her first loan was Rs. 3,000 in 2005, and her last amount was Rs. 2 lakh in February 2025. She invested the money in her sweet shop, which started in her village. She informed that the family had no agricultural land. Her husband was a motor mechanic. They had two sons, and both were married. So she fully devoted her time at the sweet shop, from where her net monthly earning was Rs.50,000.

ii) b. Another member who was interviewed was Sunkara Ramastyavathi (52 years/5th pass). Her husband was involved in rice husking, i.e., paddy to rice preparation. She also borrowed several times - in 2005, Rs. 3000, and lastly, Rs. 2025 (in February), Rs. 3 lakh, which she helped her husband to expand his business. Her one son was employed, and the daughter married. So, the family was fully involved in the husking business. The net monthly was hovering around Rs 15, 000.

Case-2: Gandhi SHG

The SHG was established in 2000 with 10 women belonging to Other Caste (OC). The initial monthly saving per member was Rs.100, which was later enhanced to Rs 200. The corpus fund of the SHG was Rs.2.80 lakh, and the SHG was provided a bank loan of Rs. 20 Lakh. To get an idea about the functioning of the SHG, one member, Alivelumangutayru (47 years/10th pass, husband a marginal farmer), was interviewed. In 2005, she borrowed an amount of Rs.

1.30 lakh from the SHG, and lastly, her borrowing was Rs.2 lakh in 2019 for cloth business, which she carried out from her own house. She informed that her monthly earning was between Rs.10,000 and Rs.15,000.

Case-3: Nakshatra SHG

The SHG was set up on September 6, 2019, with eight Backward Caste(BC) and two Other Caste (OC) members. The initial monthly saving per member was Rs.100, which was later enhanced to Rs.200. The corpus fund of the SHG was 2.55 lakh. As a case, one woman member, Godthi Triveni (Widow and person with disability), was interviewed. She was around 40 years and 10th pass. She was blessed with only one daughter, who was a school student. The family did not have agricultural land. The primary source of income was tailoring, which she carried out from her house. In a query about earning income, she said the same was between Rs. 10,000 and Rs. 15,000 per month. She only made ladies' items such as blouses, petticoats, girls' dresses, etc. She borrowed Rs. 50,000 in 2020 from the SHG, and after repayment in 2024, she borrowed Rs. 1.50 lakh. While the study was conducted, she informed that repayment of the loan was going on. Being a person with a disability, she was getting Rs. 6,000 per month from the government; as mentioned already, her earning from tailoring was between Rs. 10,000 and Rs. 15,000 per month.

Case -4: Surya Teja SHG

Surya Teja SHG was established in 2007 on June 4 with one Backward Caste (BC) and nine Other Caste women. The initial saving per member was Rs. 100, which was later enhanced to Rs. 200. The corpus fund of the SHG was 2.55 lakh. One member of the SHG, Edaratulakshmi Geeta (Widow), was interviewed. She (46 years old) completed her degree and was blessed with two daughters, one of whom was married. Another daughter was pursuing her MBA. Her sources of income per month were Rs. 4,000 as a widow pension, serving as the village organisation's assistant, earning Rs. 8,000 per month, and bill collection for TV channels in the local areas Rs. 4,000; thus, total income was Rs. 16,000 per month. It is pertinent to mention that since she was a graduate, she was selected as an assistant of the village organisation (village organisation means a group of the SHGs). For keeping all papers, documents, record etc, one assistant in VO is selected.

It is evident that the women members, by joining the SHGs, greatly benefitted as many had primary or middle-level education. Also, two members were widows, and one had physical issues. It is heartening to mention that members were so confident because of the SHG, that each member borrowed several times.

Conclusion:

Since the PRA Discussion took place in the presence of SHG members and local officials, it was observed that the members' income was sustainable. The study further revealed that all the women members were earning through different trades and businesses, and they felt empowered because they were not required to ask for money from their husbands; instead, they contributed from time to time to the welfare of the families. It is evident that the women members, by joining the SHGs, greatly benefitted as many had primary or middle-level education. Also, two members were widows, and one had physical issues.

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